

Appendix 1: Inclusion and Exclusion criteria for scoping review

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Primary studies referring to individuals diagnosed with ADHD or parents/caregivers of individuals with ADHD.2. Studies describing interventions that used social media.3. Studies reporting results from the intervention.	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Manuscripts where an intervention was not investigated or were not primary studies (e.g., reviews, editorials, commentaries, letters to the editor)2. Studies not utilizing social media as an intervention.3. Studies not reporting results.

Annette BERGSLAND and Elia GABARRON: **Social media interventions for individuals with ADHD: A scoping review**

Appendix 2. Search Terms entered in database search

Categories	Search Terms
ADHD	ADHD, Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder, Hyperactivity disorder, Attention-Deficit Disorder
Social Media	Social media, Social networking, Facebook, YouTube, WhatsApp, Messenger, Instagram, WeChat, Kuaishou, TikTok, Telegram, Qzone, QQ, Weibo, Douyin, Snapchat, Twitter, Pinterest, Reddit, LinkedIn, Quora, Skype

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Appendix 3. Grey literature search

Google Scholar	<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ First 100 entries in Google Scholar were examined for relevance, using search words, ADHD and social media intervention.
Conference proceedings Snowballing	<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Scandinavian Health Informatics Conference, 2022○ Medical Informatics Europe Conference (MIE)<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Geneva, 2020▪ Athens, 2021▪ Nice, 2022▪ Gothenburg, 2023○ Reference lists of relevant publications
Organizations for individuals with ADHD	<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ ADHD Norway (https://www.adhdnorge.no/)○ Children and Adults with Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (chadd.org)